

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**“A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY OF COLLECTION,
SEGREGATION AND DISPOSAL OF HOSPITAL WASTE
MANAGEMENT AT A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL OF
LAHORE”**

Dr. Hateem Bakhsh Sobhi¹, Dr. Ali Hussnain², Dr. Mahrukh Mumtaz³

¹House Officer at Jinnah Hospital Lahore, Email: hateembakhsh95@yahoo.com

²Medical Officer at THQ Hospital Bhagtanwala, Sargodha, Email: ahshah12@hotmail.com.

³Woman Medical Officer at Akbar Niazi Teaching Hospital/ANTH, Islamabad,
Email: mahrukhmumtaz23@gmail.com.

Article Received: June 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** July 2020**Abstract:**

Introduction: Any unwanted or undesired material which was useful but now rendered un-useful is called waste. Wastes are divided into two groups, Non-Hazardous waste and hazardous waste. Non-Hazardous waste is not usually the risk of health, whereas Hazardous waste is the causes of many health risks. Biomedical or healthcare waste (HCW) or Medical waste is a term for all waste that arises in a medical facility.

Methodology:

STUDY DESIGN: Cross Sectional Descriptive Study

PLACE OF STUDY: Lahore General hospital (LGH) is the one of the largest complex tertiary care teaching institution of 860 beds, attached with Postgraduate medical institute Lahore and is situated in high density populated southern area of Lahore. LGH is in contract with Private Company Lahore for biomedical waste disposal generated in this hospital through incinerator, but proper waste management system is not present even in Dialysis center.

SAMPLE SIZE

1.All biomedical waste generating units which were 52 in number.

2.All persons (72) involved in waste generation disposal and management working in different wards of LGH.

Results: Out of 72 persons interviewed 48 (66.67%) were female and 24 (33.33%) were male. Regarding marital status 54 (75%) were married, 18 (25%) were single. Regarding Education 5 (6.94%) of them were graduate, 7 (9.72%) were post graduate, 8 (11.11%) were Matric, 13 (18.06%) were under matric and 33 (45.84%) were illiterate which were mostly Sanitary Workers. Regarding Income status 25 (34.73%) persons were earning Rs;26,000 to 50,000, 21 (29.17%) persons were earning Rs; 10,000 to25,000, 21 (29.17%) persons were earning Rs; 51,000 to Rs; 75,000 and 5 (6.93%) was earning Rs; 76,000 to 100, 000.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Hateem Bakhsh Sobhi,

House Officer at Jinnah Hospital Lahore,

Email: hateembakhsh95@yahoo.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press Hateem Bakhsh Sobhi et al., A Cross-Sectional Study Of Collection, Segregation And Disposal Of Hospital Waste Management At A Tertiary Care Hospital Of Lahore , Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07[07]

INTRODUCTION:

Any unwanted or undesired material which was useful but now rendered un-useful is called waste. Wastes are divided into two groups, Non-Hazardous waste and hazardous waste. Non-Hazardous waste is not usually the risk of health, whereas Hazardous waste is the causes of many health risks. Biomedical or healthcare waste (HCW) or Medical waste is a term for all waste that arises in a medical facility. Risk-free or conventional medical waste (paper, packaging, food waste, etc.). Between 75-90% HCW is compared to household waste³. Biological wastes produced in different hospitals constitute 85% of non-hazardous and 15% hazardous waste, of which 11% of infectious waste and 4% of inefficient waste. The remaining 10-25% (15% in% of 15%, India between 15-35% and Pakistan 20%) are considered as a risk for health workers (poverty, psychiatry, acid, etc.) and create a variety of health risk⁴. The decrease in paper is reduced due to the continuous trend and high use of disposable items. Of infectious waste, more than plastic containers, intravenous lines and paper wrappers are defined for sterile instrument sets that were not infectious⁵.

Although Hazardous wastes are generated in small quantities, they are potentially infectious and injurious to human health and environment. These infectious wastes are also known as biomedical wastes. The main sources of biomedical wastes are hospitals, health care establishments, health clinics, medical research diagnostic laboratories, treatment or immunization of human beings and animals, physician's offices, dentists, health care Homes, Dialysis center, diabetic centers and funeral homes⁶.

Biological waste is different from other dangerous waste like industrial and kitchen waste, that means they come from biological sources or to diagnose, prevent or cure diseases. It is described as biological waste: "Solid or liquid waste which may pose a risk to humans, including non-liquid tissues; Body parts, blood, blood products and body fluids of humans and other primates; Laboratory and veterinary waste containing human pathogens; and discarded sharp objects. Use of absorbent material, blood, blood products, body fluids or secretions contaminated with visible blood; Non-absorbent disposable instruments that may be contaminated with blood, body fluids or secretions, or secretions that are visually contaminated with blood but can not be treated by approved methods⁷.

In developing countries like Pakistan the waste management practices are inadequate due to lack of political commitment, scarcity of resources, Casual behavior of hospital authorities, Lack of legislation and its implementation. The information regarding waste management practices is extremely deficient in Pakistan. The expected information may help the community to understand the consequences of

improper management of biomedical wastes and government and major non-government organizations in policy making for legislation to implement strictly.

To fulfill this deficiency, a small effort was done to conduct this study. Lahore General Hospital Lahore was selected for this study because no study has been conducted so far in this hospital to assess the HWM practices. The study was conducted to assess the current status of biomedical wastes practices in Lahore General Hospital.

This study would assess the practices regarding HWM in Lahore General Hospital Lahore and will help in reduction of infectious diseases due to inappropriate handling of these hazardous wastes. It will also generate recommendations for better practices in hospital.

METHODOLOGY:**STUDY DESIGN**

Cross Sectional Descriptive Study

PLACE OF STUDY

Lahore General hospital (LGH) is the one of the largest complex tertiary care teaching institution of 860 beds, attached with Postgraduate medical institute Lahore and is situated in high density populated southern area of Lahore. LGH is in contract with Private Company Lahore for biomedical waste disposal generated in this hospital through incinerator, but proper waste management system is not present even in Dialysis center. This hospital is comprised of more than 44 wards/Departments and 08 Operation Theatres.

STUDY POPULATION

All biomedical waste generating 52 wards/departments of Lahore General Hospital, Lahore including 04 units of general surgery, 04 units of general Medicine, 03 units of Gynecology &obstetrics, 02 units of ENT, and 01 units each of Cardiology, Urology, Oncology, Ophthalmology, Dermatology, ICU, Cardiac surgery, Plastic surgery, Neurosurgery, Dental surgery, Radiotherapy, Orthopedics, Radiology, Emergency pharmacy, Pathology, Blood Bank, Accident and Emergency Department and one Dialysis center consisting of 12 units, 8 operation theater and persons involved in biomedical waste management. 72 persons of Lahore Hospital Lahore, involved in waste generation, disposal and management were included in the study.

SAMPLE SIZE

- 1.All biomedical waste generating units which were 52 in number.
- 2.All persons (72) involved in waste generation disposal and management working in different wards of LGH.

STUDY UNIT

Biomedical waste generating unit and staff involved in HWM.

RESULTS:

Lahore General Hospital is a Public Teaching Hospital, situated in District Lahore. 72 persons were interviewed who were working in different wards of different departments in the Hospital Total outdoor patients in 2014 were 9, 62,544 (2674 patient per day), Total indoor patients were 40,564 (783 patient per day), Total number of wards / departments were 75, total number of bed were 860, Total operation/procedures done were 75,596, total number of pathological test done were 23,26,234, total quantity of biomedical waste was 645 kg per day and total person interviewed working in different ward were 72. Socio-demographic characteristics of person interviewed working in different wards of Lahore General Hospital Lahore. Out of 72 persons interviewed most of persons 26

(36.11%) were of age group 41- 50 years, 20 (27.78%) persons were of age group 21-30 years, 14 (19.44%) persons were of age group 31-40 years and 12 (16.67%) persons were of age group 51-60 years (Table 1).

Out of 72 persons interviewed 48 (66.67%) were female and 24 (33.33%) were male. Regarding marital status 54

(75%) were married, 18 (25%) were single. Regarding Education 5 (6.94%) of them were graduate, 7 (9.72%) were post graduate, 8 (11.11%) were Matric, 13 (18.06%) were under matric and 33 (45.84%) were illiterate which were mostly Sanitary Workers. Regarding Income status 25 (34.73%) persons were earning Rs;26,000 to 50,000, 21 (29.17%) persons were earning Rs; 10,000 to25,000, 21 (29.17%) persons were earning Rs; 51,000 to Rs; 75,000 and 5 (6.93%) was earning Rs; 76,000 to 100, 000.

Frequency Distribution according to age group(n=72)

Age Group	Frequency	Percentage
21-30	20	27.78%
31-40	14	19.44%
41-50	26	36.11%
51-60	12	16.67%

Frequency Distribution according to Sex of persons (n = 72)

Female	48	66.67%
Male	24	33.33%

Frequency Distribution according to Marital Status (n = 72)

Single	18	25%
Married	54	75%

Frequency distribution of container used for biomedical waste collection and Transportation in wards / Departments (n=75)

Containers used for biomedical waste collection	Frequency	Percent
Plastic bins	72	96%
Plastic Bags	73	97.33%
Cardboard puncture proof	71	94.66%
Wheel barrows	5	6.94%
Covered carts	67	93.05%
Trolleys	Nil	0.00%
Open baskets	Nil	0.00%

Frequency distribution of qualification of persons interviewed in respect to knowledge about training given to newly hired staff for waste management (n=72)

Qualification	Knowledge of training to new employees for waste management				
	Yes	Percentage	No	Percentage	Total
Illiterate / Undermatric	7 (New)	50%	7 Already trained	50%	14
Literate	28 (New)	48.28%	30 Already trained	51.72%	58
Total	35	48.61%	37	51.39%	72

DISCUSSION:

The population of Islamic Republic of Pakistan is 184.7 million (United Nations, 2010). A large number of hospital waste incinerators are being installed in many health-care establishments in Pakistan without any competent guidelines and proper legislation control. Awareness about consumption of potentially hazardous air is raising in public (for example, dioxins, hormones, furans, extrusion of rubber, HCl, cadmium and lead) and due to incinerators plants disadvantages of potentially hazardous residues (eg, cadmium and lead contents) Transfer to environment is forcing users to shift to more environmental friendly options like microwave, chemical disinfection, autoclaving and wet thermal treatments. The purpose of treating and disposal of dangerous medical waste is to reduce the risks, but the release of toxic pollutants into the environment as a result of treatment or disposal may lead to indirect health risks. Modern incinerators plants work with special scrubbers at 800-11000c, due to which do not form dioxins and furans or just minor amounts are produced³⁷. In response to the increase in environmental problems, the Government of Pakistan reported on the hospital waste management rules in 2005, the methods of handling waste for the separate storage, transportation and hospital wastes disposal in a safe manner. The hospital administrators should follow procedures according to law to protect the public from coming into contact with biomedical wastes³². The absence of an EH unit/division is one of the major factor in controlling and monitoring the Environment Health (EH) which is contributing the poor health. Environmental Health Unit (EHU) was established in March 1997 on Adhoc basis in the Ministry of Health (MOH) with the financial and technical assistance of WHO to support environmental health activities in the country. The main aim of the programmers was to develop National Resource Center for all issues pertaining to EH ranging from environmental pollution, municipal and hospital waste management,

chemical safety, drinking water quality, water supply and sanitation, information systems management and control³⁶.

A number of planned activities in 1996/97 were implemented successfully. However, in December 1998, the EHU was shifted to Health Services Academy (HSA) due to the lack of available resources and to improve coordination among various units and departments within Ministry of Health (MoH). The HSA with all its available resources attempted to implement planned EH activities to date and provided technical support. The EHU at Health Services Academy, with the support of WHO has been able to give technical inputs in finalizing the Hospital Waste Management Rules 2005 (notified), prepared hospital waste management guidelines, prepared Drinking Water Quality Standards for Pakistan (2007), prepared manuals for workers for their occupational health (2005), prepared implementation plan for health care waste management (2006) and initiatives on children environmental health. The EHU has also prepared a PC-1 for establishment of EHU at federal level and at provincial levels. Recently (2007) a project for the development of a National Healthcare Waste Management Action Plan has begun in collaboration with WHO³⁶. The Pakistan Environmental Protection Act (PEPA), 1997, clearly defines hazardous and hospital waste under the subsections XIX and XXI respectively. The handling of hazardous waste is mentioned under the subsection 14. Hospital Waste Management Draft Rules, 2002 were prepared by the Ministry of Environment and Environmental Health Unit (EHU). These Draft Rules were distributed widely to all the provincial health departments and other stakeholders for their comments. Now, these Rules have been notified by the Government of Pakistan in 2005 [SRO 1013 (1)/2005, 3rd August 2005]. EHU-Ministry of Health has also prepared the Hospital and Biomedical Waste Management Guidelines to elaborate various kinds of wastes, their risks to human health; formation of waste management

teams, plan; waste segregation; color coding; protective clothing for waste handlers; waste collection, transportation, storage, and disposal; handling accidents and spillages; and waste minimization and reuse³⁷. In many ways the current management of hospital waste was wrong. There was no record of people who are responsible for the mismanagement. He also said that the waste cleaners are not given any goods or training for proper handling of the hospital wastes. Hospital's waste management rules for 2005 should be implemented in all the hospitals through the establishment of committees and hospital waste management teams³⁷.

Study of non-governmental organization has shown that 80,000 tons of daily solid waste produced. Hospital waste ingredients are up to 15 to 20 percent, but it is mixed with solid waste, and thus polluted the whole batch. Studies are prepared for waste / bed / day of about 2 kg, in which 0.1-0.5 percent can be attributed to the risk of health. Due to lack of safety measures the cases of hepatitis B and C has been increased in the country, with the average incidence of hepatitis B 3-4% (6 million) and hepatitis C, 5% (7.5 million). About 250,000 tons of medical wastes in Pakistan are annually produced from medical institutions (state of Environmental Report, 2005, Government of Pakistan)³². A study by Scott and Praphy and NESPAK (1997) has found that waste of state hospital in Karachi is 1.63 kg / bed / day and 3.69 kg / bed / day, averaging about 3.02 kilograms per bed per day. In the private hospitals in Karachi, breeds were estimated at 5.13 kg /bed / day. According to these results, total hospital waste produced in Karachi is estimated to be 100 tons per day³². The guidelines on medical waste suggest that the infectious waste material can be treated as more malicious or properly packaged to reduce the risk of exposing others³⁰. The disposal of medical waste is an integral part of infection control and hygiene programs in medical facilities²⁸. Proper disposal of medical waste is regulated by organization, as well as relevant legislation, funding and the active participation of trained and informative personnel²⁰.

CONCLUSION:

Health care waste management practices in Lahore General Hospital Lahore were in better shape but general awareness of this problem is lacking among both waste generators and processors. Better practices observed at Lahore General Hospital Lahore are most probably due to better government structure, practices and adequate funding. Data, information and data were not mentioned about biological waste management, sources, submission, collection, transportation and handling. No studies have been made by Municipalities, EPA and any state institutions.

REFERENCES:

1. Visvanathan, Adhikari R. Healthcare Waste Management in South Asia. [Online].2006 sep. [2011 May 27]; Available from:www.environment.gov.pk/pub-pdf/.../Part3-Chp%207.pdf.
2. Ilyas M. Public Health and Community Medicine. 7th ed. Karachi (Pakistan): Time Publisher; 2008: P. 275-81.
3. Park K. Park's textbook of preventive and social medicine. 18th ed. Jabalpur (India): M/s BanarsidasBhanot; 2007-8: p. 595-99.
4. Pruss, A, Cirouit, E, and Rushbrook, P. Safe management of wastes from healthcare Activities. WHO, 1999. Available at: www.medwasteind.org/Journal/journal1%205.1.pdf
5. Rutala WA, Odette RL, Samsa GP. Management of Infectious waste by US hospitals JAMA.[Online]. 1989 [cited 2004 Sep 14]; 262(12): 1635-40. Available from:www.ipac.kacst.edu.sa/eDoc/2004/14284.0.1-20040300181.pdf
6. World Health Organization. Wastes from health-care activities. [online].2007 [2011jun10];(1). Available from: www.who.int/mediacentre/factsheets/fs253/en
7. State of Florida department of health Bureau of Community. Environmental Health. [online]. 2011 updated! FDOH Proposes New Changes to Chapter 64E-16 Florida Administrative Code for Biomedical Waste; Available from: www.sharpsmd.net/fdoh/florida-biomedical-waste-policy-chapter-64
8. Agathos N. Hospital Waste Factsheet by WWF. [online]. 2010 [2011 Jun 10];(1). Available from: http://www.wfpak.org/factsheets_hwf.php
9. Oweisa R, Mohamad A, Widyamb, Ohood A, Limoon A. Medical waste management in Jordan: King Hussein Medical Centre Biomedical Engineering Department, Jordan University of Science and Technology. [online]. 2005 Mar25 [cited2005jun8];[622-625]. Available from: www.elsevier.com/locate/wasma
10. Shahida Rasheed, Saira Iqbal, Lubna A, Baig, Kehkashan Mufti. JPMA. Hospital Waste Management in the Teaching Hospitals of Karachi. [online].2005 [2011 Jun 12];(1). Available from:www.jpma.org.pk/full_article_text.php?article_id=737
11. Agathos N. Hospital Waste Factsheet by WWF. [online].2010 [2011 Jun 10]; (1). Available from: http://www.wfpak.org/factsheets_hwf.php
12. Park K. Park's textbook of preventive and social medicine. 18th ed. Jabalpur (India): M/s BanarsidasBhanot; 2009:P. 694-99.

13. Surjit S. Katoch. Biomedical Waste Classified and Prevailing Management Strategies.[online].2007 [2011 Jun11];(1). Available from: www.swlf.ait.ac.th/Int/Conf/Data/.../4_06%20_SS%20Katoch.pdf
14. Manyele SV, Lyasenga TJ. Effects of improper hospital-waste management on Occupational health and safety. Factors affecting medical waste management in low level health facilities in Tanzania.[online].2010 [2010 Mar 18];4(5): 304-318. Available from:<http://www.academicjournals.org/AJEST> ISSN 1991-637X©2010 Academic Journals.
15. Park K. Park's textbook of preventive and social medicine. 18th ed. Jabalpur (India): M/s BanarsidasBhanot; 2007-8: P. 595-99.
16. Manyele S V, Lyasenga TJ. Effects of improper hospital-waste management on occupational health and safety.Factors affecting medical waste management in low level health facilities in Tanzania. [online]. 2010 [2010 Mar 18];4(5):304-318:Available from: <http://www.academicjournals.org/AJEST> ISSN 1991-637X (c) 2010 Academic Journals.
17. Park K. Park's textbook of preventive and social medicine. 20th ed. Jabalpur (India): M/s BanarsidasBhanot; 2009: P. 295-299.
18. Magdy AB, Salam EI. Hospital waste management in EI-Beheira Governorate EgyptMagda.Overview of biomedical waste management in selected government.Environmental Health Department, High Institute of Public Health, Alexandria university, 165 EI-Horreya Avenue, Alexandria, Egypt. [online]. 2009[cited 2009 Dec 8]; Science Direct Journal of Environmental Management journal homepage: Available from: [www.elsevier.com/locate/jenvman,0301-4797/\\$](http://www.elsevier.com/locate/jenvman,0301-4797/$)
19. Rehan A, Arnold van de K. UWEP research coordinator and UWEP director WASTE advisers on urban environment and development GoudaCase. Study Report Special Waste Fractions: Hospital Waste Management in Pakistan waste. [online]. 1997 Aug [cited 1998 Apr; (pages 102). Available from: <http://www.waste.nl>
20. ShahidaRasheed, SairaIqbal, Lubna A, Baig, Kehkashan Mufti. JPMA.Hospital Waste Management in the Teaching Hospitals of Karachi. [online].2005[2011 Jun12];(1). Available from: www.jpma.org.pk/full_article_text.php?article_id=737
21. Pescod MB. Professor Dr, Saw Gouda C.B.A synthesis report UWEP Working Document 8. The Netherlands, Hospital Waste Management in Four Major Cities. [online]. 1997 Aug [cited 1998 feb;(pages 102). Available from: <http://www.waste.nl>
22. Askarian et al, 2004a; Marinkovic et al, 2005; Rasheed et al, 2005. Overview of biomedical waste management in selected. Waste disposal is governed by laws of the Ministry of Environmental In Egypt.[online].2005[cited 2007 Dec 12]; (10)(pages 1920-23); Available From: www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0956053X06002583
23. Sahar Mohamed Soliman I, Amel Ibrahim Ahmed. Overview of biomedical waste management in selected Governorates in Egypt. Department of Community Health Nursing, Faculty of Nursing, Mansoura university,Egypt.[online].2006Aug16.[2006 oct 27];(1). Available from:app6.mans.edu.eg/mus/Future/.../UploadDownloadFile.py
24. Visvanathan I, Adhikari R. Health care Waste Management in South Asia.[online]. 2006 [cited 2011 jun 12]; 3(1). Availabel from:www.environment.gov.pk/pub-pdf/Part3-Chp%207.pdf
25. Akter M. A Review Medical Waste Management.Asian Institute of Technlogy Thailand. [online]. 2000[cited 2000 Jan].(1). Available from: <http://www.eng-consult.com/BEN/papers/Paper-anasima.pdf>
26. Rao, H.V.N. 3rd International Conference Appropriate Waste Management Technology for Developing Countries. Disposal of Hospital Wastes in Bangalore and their Impact on Environment. [online]. 1995 Feb 25[cited 1995 Feb 26]. Nagpur, Technical Papers Vol. II.)
27. Hospital Waste factsheet. wwfpak organization: Available from: http://www.wwfpak.org/factsheets_hwf.php
28. Sahar Mohamed Soliman I, Amel Ibrahim Ahmed. Overview of biomedical waste management in selected Governorates in Egypt. Department of Community Health Nursing, Faculty of Nursing, Mansoura University, Egypt. [online]. 2006Aug 16. [2006 oct 27];(1). Available from:app6.mans.edu.eg/mus/Future/.../UploadDownloadFile.py
29. NasimaAkt. Environmental Engineering Program School of Environment, Resources and Development, Asian Institute of Technology Khlongluang, Pathumthani 12120, Thailand.A Review Medical Waste Management. [online]. Available from:www.Nakter@excite.com
30. Visvanathan, Adhikari R. Healthcare Waste Management in South Asia. [online]. 2006 sep.[2011 May 27.];(1). Available

- from::www.environment.gov.pk/pub-pdf/.../Part3-Chp%207.pdf
31. NasimaAkter, AMR Chowdhury, KaziNM.Environmental Evaluation Medical Waste Disposal in Dhaka City Hospital. Waste Disposal in Bangladesh with Special Reference to Dhaka City and its Environmental Evaluation.[online].1999 [cited 2003 Feb 12];(87). Available from: www.bracresearch.org/reports/hospital_waste.pdf
 32. Visvanathan I, Adhikari R. Health care Waste Management in South Asia.[online]. 2006 [cited 2011 jun 12]; 3(1). Available from::www.environment.gov.pk/pub-pdf /Part3-Chp%207.pdf
 33. World Health Organization. Wastes from health-care activities. [online]. 2007. [2011 jun,10];(1). Available from: :www.who.int/mediacentre/ Factsheets/fs253
 34. NasimaAkter, AMR Chowdhury, KaziNM.Environmental Evaluation Medical Waste Disposal in Dhaka City Hospital.Waste Disposal in Bangladesh with Special Reference to Dhaka City and its Environmental Evaluation. [online].1999 [cited 2003 Feb 12];(87). Available from: www.bracresearch.org/reprots/hospital_waste.pdf
 35. World Health Organization. Wastes from health-care activities. [online]. 2007. [2011 jun 10];(1). Available from::www.who.int/mediacentre/factsheets/fs 253/en
 36. ElahiJohriA E. Environmental Health Profile of Pakistan Hospital Waste Management. World Health Organization Government of Pakistan WHO Country Office Pakistan Regional, Centre for Environmental Health Activities (CEHA), Amman, Jordan. [online].2000 oct[cited 2005 sep 12]; Available from: www.environment.gov.pk
 37. Rehan A, Arnold van de K. UWEP research coordinator and UWEP director WASTE advisers on urban environment and developmentGoudaCase. Study Report Special Waste Fractions:Hospital Waste Management in Pakistanwaste. [online]. 1997 Aug [cited 1998 Apr];(pages 102). Available from: http://www.waste.nl